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The "Compendium of Research Abstracts for Research in Education" is a semiannual publication by the Green Valley College Foundation Inc. This unique compilation serves as a dynamic showcase of the institution's latest research endeavors in the field of education. Each edition features a collection of research abstracts representing diverse topics and methodologies explored by the institution's faculty and scholars.

Published twice a year, this Compendium is a testament to the commitment of Green Valley College Foundation Inc. to foster a culture of research and academic excellence. The featured papers have successfully passed the rigorous institutional editorial and panel review, ensuring the quality and adherence to scholarly standards. While these papers are considered pre-prints and have not undergone external peer review, they provide valuable insights into the ongoing research landscape within the institution.

The Compendium serves as a platform for researchers to disseminate their preliminary findings, spark discussions, and invite collaboration within the academic community. By offering a glimpse into the cutting-edge research conducted at Green Valley College Foundation Inc., this publication contributes to the ongoing dialogue in the field of education and lays the groundwork for future scholarly endeavors.

TABLE OF CONTENT

Research Title	Page Number
USABILITY OF CLOZE TEST TOWARD READING SKILLS AMONG INTERMEDIATE PUPILS AT CROSSING DIAZ ELEMENTARY SCHOOL, CITY OF KORONADAL, SOUTH COTABATO, PHILIPPINES	3
TRANSITION OF MODALITIES: LEARNERS' PERCEPTIONS AND LEARNING STYLES AMONG GRADE 6 STUDENTS AT OSITA CENTRAL ELEMENTARY SCHOOL	4
TEACHERS' PERSPECTIVE: LEARNING BEHAVIOR OF GENERATION ALPHA LEARNERS	5
MOTIVATION AND LEARNING STRATEGIES OF FIRST YEAR AND SECOND YEAR BACHELOR OF ELEMENTARY EDUCATION STUDENTS IN HYBRID MODALITY AT GREEN VALLEY COLLEGE FOUNDATION INC.	6
CHALLENGES OF STRUGGLING READERS AMONG INTERMEDIATE PUPILS: THE AFTERMATH PANDEMIC AT STO. NIÑO ELEMENTARY SCHOOL, CITY OF KORONADAL, SOUTH COTABATO, PHILIPPINES	7
SELF-EFFICACY AND READINESS OF THIRD YEAR BACHELOR OF ELEMENTARY EDUCATION PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS AT GREEN VALLEY COLLEGE FOUNDATION INC.: BASIS FOR PROPOSED ENHANCEMENT WORKSHOP	8

¹ USABILITY OF CLOZE TEST TOWARD READING SKILLS AMONG INTERMEDIATE PUPILS AT CROSSING DIAZ ELEMENTARY SCHOOL, CITY OF KORONADAL, SOUTH COTABATO, PHILIPPINES

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Keywords: Cloze test, reading comprehension, pronunciation, pre-test, post-test.

ABSTRACT

This research aimed to investigate the reading skills of intermediate pupils, focusing on pronunciation and reading comprehension. The study employed the cloze test to assess these skills and also examined the usability of the cloze test in this context. This research falls into the category of quasi-experimental research, utilizing an intermediate-level pretest and posttest design.

The study's target population consisted of 98 intermediate pupils at Crossing Diaz Elementary School during the academic year 2022-2023. The researchers employed a total sampling technique, selecting 51 males and 47 females as the sample group. The research instrument used was a questionnaire adapted from Phil-IRI.

Data was collected from pre-test and post-test results, followed by analysis using statistical techniques. The analysis aimed to identify significant differences in students' pronunciation and reading comprehension abilities before and after the administration of the cloze test. In this study, the researcher utilized the t-test for paired samples to compare means. Upon analysis, the pre-test mean score was 9.265306122, which was higher than the posttest mean score of 7.66326531. This indicates a difference in the mean scores of pupils' pronunciation and reading comprehension between the pretest and post-test. The findings revealed a p-value of 1.35961E-06, which is less than .05, signifying that the pretest scores were significantly higher than the post-test scores. Consequently, these results suggest that the cloze test may not be a suitable assessment tool.

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SOE-2023-RE-0001 (Research in Education)

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¹TRANSITION OF MODALITIES: LEARNERS' PERCEPTIONS AND LEARNING STYLES AMONG GRADE 6 STUDENTS AT OSITA CENTRAL ELEMENTARY SCHOOL, KORONADAL CITY, PHILIPPINES

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Perceptions. Transition of modalities, learning styles

ABSTRACT

This study investigates how students' perceptions and preferred learning styles changed as they transitioned from modular to face-to-face instruction. Previous studies focused on higher grade levels but did not provide more information on elementary students. The researchers aim to address this issue at the elementary level.

This study, a correlational analysis, aims to determine the significant relationship between the perceptions and preferred learning modalities of sixth-grade students at Osita Central Elementary School. The respondents were chosen through simple random sampling from among the 130 grade 6 students at Osita Central Elementary School who were formally enrolled by the school year 2022-2023. Using Pearson's coefficient, one can determine how significant student perceptions and learning preferences are.

Researchers found a marginally negative correlation between participants' learning perceptions and learning style (Pearson's coefficient = -0.206). This suggests that as learners' perceptions change, their learning styles shift slightly in the opposite direction. Further research and consideration of other factors are needed to fully understand the interaction between learning perceptions and styles. Supporting learners' needs and fostering metacognition can improve overall learning experiences through individualized instruction.

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¹TEACHERS' PERSPECTIVE: LEARNING BEHAVIOR OF GENERATION ALPHA LEARNERS

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Keywords:

Perspective, learning behavior, generalization alpha learners.

ABSTRACT

This study utilized a descriptive quantitative research design to explore the learning behavior of Generation Alpha learners in Koronadal Central Elementary School II from the perspective of their teachers. The study aimed to provide a static picture of the situation and establish the relationship between different variables. The researchers formulated a survey questionnaire that was checked by five experts in the field of education and was validated using Content Validity Ratio (CVR) with Lawshe Method. The questionnaire was divided into four parts, which focused on the responsibility, perseverance, collaboration, and initiative of Generation Alpha learners. The reliability of the survey questionnaire was also measured using test and pre-test reliability to ensure that the data gathered were reliable and valid.

The study found that there were no significant differences between collaboration, initiative, perseverance, and responsibility among the respondents. The study also identified several practical strategies that teachers can use to create a positive and effective learning environment for Generation Alpha learners, such as incorporating technology in the classroom, using active learning strategies, and providing opportunities for social interaction. The study concludes that descriptive quantitative studies are helpful in describing how one occurrence is related to another, especially when the researcher has no control over the independent variables. Overall, the study provides valuable insights into the learning behavior of Generation Alpha learners and highlights the importance of using appropriate research designs to gather reliable and valid data.

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SOE-2023-RE-0003 (Research in Education)

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¹ MOTIVATION AND LEARNING STRATEGIES OF FIRST YEAR AND SECOND YEAR BACHELOR OF ELEMENTARY EDUCATION STUDENTS IN HYBRID MODALITY AT GREEN VALLEY COLLEGE FOUNDATION INC.

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Keywords: motivation, learning strategies, correlation.

ABSTRACT

The motivation levels of college education students were significantly impacted by the abrupt shift to online learning in response to the COVID-19 pandemic in 2019. Many educational institutions have since adopted hybrid learning, which combines in-person and online classes. This study surveyed 297 education students currently enrolled at Green Valley College Foundation Inc. during the Second Semester of the 2022-2023 school year, selected through random stratified sampling. Data was collected using a Likert Scale and a survey questionnaire to interpret the results.

The study's findings indicate that students expressed a high level of motivation for learning, both in online and face-to-face classes. They frequently employed various learning strategies to facilitate self-paced learning. Furthermore, a positive correlation was observed between the utilization of learning strategies and academic achievement. The frequency of employing these strategies significantly predicted students' academic success in a hybrid learning environment.

These results suggest that, with proper support, assistance, and encouragement, students can remain motivated in both online and face-to-face learning settings, despite the challenges. Additionally, future research could explore and compare the motivation and utilization of learning strategies among students in both basic education and higher education, encompassing both public and private sectors.

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SOE-2023-RE-0004 (Research in Education)

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¹ CHALLENGES OF STRUGGLING READERS AMONG INTERMEDIATE PUPILS: THE AFTERMATH PANDEMIC AT STO. NIÑO ELEMENTARY SCHOOL, CITY OF KORONADAL, SOUTH COTABATO, PHILIPPINES

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ABSTRACT

This qualitative study aimed to investigate the challenges faced by struggling readers among intermediate pupils at Sto. Niño Elementary School in the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic. The study utilized a narrative-qualitative research design, which involved collecting and analyzing non-numerical data to understand the concepts of the challenges of struggling readers. An adapted interview form was used to determine the primary and secondary sources of the data, with the teacher's response serving as the researchers' secondary source of information.

The findings of the study revealed that struggling readers faced several challenges during the pandemic, including difficulties in accessing learning materials, lack of motivation, and limited support from parents and guardians. The study also identified several successful interventions and strategies that have been implemented to help struggling readers catch up, including implementing a comprehensive and sustained reading program, administering particular reading analyses, maintaining compatible proficiency in reading across various courses, and regularly monitoring and evaluating students' progress. The study's results have significant implications for educators and policymakers, as they provide insight into the difficulties experienced by struggling readers among intermediate students in the aftermath of the pandemic. By recognizing and addressing these issues, educators and governments may establish tailored interventions to help these children's academic success and well-being. The study also highlights the importance of personalized approaches to teaching struggling readers by taking into account their individual needs and learning styles. Overall, this study contributes to the current body of literature on the challenges of struggling readers and provides valuable insights into effective interventions and strategies to support their academic achievement.

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¹ SELF-EFFICACY AND READINESS OF THIRD YEAR BACHELOR OF ELEMENTARY EDUCATION PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS AT GREEN VALLEY COLLEGE FOUNDATION INC.

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the self-efficacy and readiness of third-year Bachelor of Elementary Education pre-service teachers at Green Valley College Foundation, Inc. The researchers utilized a quantitative research method with a descriptive research design to gather data through an adapted survey questionnaire. The participants were all active third-year BEED students, with a total of 101 respondents. The findings revealed that the pre-service teachers had a high level of self-efficacy and readiness in terms of classroom management, teaching strategies, professional development, and socio-emotional aspects. However, there were still areas for improvement, particularly in the areas of classroom management and socio-emotional aspects.

The study also found that attending enhancement workshops, specifically in-service training, could help pre-service teachers gain additional knowledge and understanding in these areas. Overall, this study provides valuable insights into the self-efficacy and readiness of pre-service teachers and highlights the importance of continuous learning and development in the teaching profession.

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